

MODERN STRATEGIES AND DEVELOPMENTS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE INSTRUCTION

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Abstract: The article emphasises the necessity of maintaining a dynamic approach to foreign language teaching, ensuring that methodologies remain aligned with the evolving demands and circumstances of the modern educational landscape. The article notes that the issue is extensively represented in scholarly research, reflecting various aspects and contexts. The objective of this research is to analyse contemporary approaches and trends in the methodology of teaching foreign languages at higher education institutions. The study focuses on the methodology of teaching foreign languages at these institutions. The research methodology combines scientific methods and approaches, including analysing scholarly research and publications, systematising current trends, and utilising theoretical modelling. The findings demonstrate the most recent developments in foreign language teaching, effective in traditional, distance, and blended learning environments. In order to implement updated methodological tools, instructors must receive appropriate training. It was demonstrated that the selection of teaching tools has a significant impact on the effectiveness of the teaching strategy. It shows the potential flexibility of contemporary trends following the direction of professional education. In light of the findings above, several illustrative exercises are presented which may be employed in the learning process. Implementing such methodologies necessitates adherence to the systematisation and structuring of educational material. The study presents a series of credible directions for enforcing modern approaches and trends in teaching foreign languages in Ukrainian higher education institutions. In conclusion, this research direction has considerable potential due to its dynamism and progressiveness.

Keywords: higher education institution, communicative competence, educational technology, blended learning, distance learning, CLIL technology, reading comprehension of an informational text, content area vocabulary

1 Introduction

Educational processes are no exception in today's world, where technology is increasingly applied across various life spheres. It is particularly relevant to foreign language education, where new technologies can positively influence the development of students' communicative competence. Simultaneously, changes in the scientific approach to language learning necessitate new methodologies and technologies for effectively developing students' active and passive vocabulary in higher education institutions.

The relevance of this article lies in the need to explore new approaches to language learning in the context of modern technological advancement. This research's findings could be helpful for educators seeking to identify and implement effective teaching methods and students looking for innovative methods for personal and professional self-development. Additionally, the issue of vocabulary development is pertinent due to the shift in perception of language education as a system for developing communicative competence, in which vocabulary is a crucial component.

This study aims to analyse current approaches and trends in teaching foreign languages in higher education institutions.

2 Literature review

Uyun (2020) emphasised the importance of considering the instructional strategy as a crucial aspect of the teaching process. Determining appropriate learning strategies can significantly enhance educational outcomes. Khansir et al. (2021) observed that a learning strategy should be explicitly aligned with educational objectives and encompass the selection of

appropriate instructional aids. Miranda and Wahyudin (2023) identified factors that neither contribute to success nor failure in language learning. However, these factors must be understood by educators if they wish to aid students in more successful English language acquisition.

Zapotichna and Romanyuk (2020) highlight new trends in foreign language teaching, focusing on interactive approaches and Communicative Language Teaching (CLT). Adebileje and Akinola (2020) comprehensively analysed various language teaching and learning theories, including behaviourist, cognitive, humanistic, habit formation, intellectual capacities, and student motivation. The teaching theories discussed include formal-functional, traditional grammatical, structuralist, transformational generative grammar, audio-linguistic, functional-notional, direct method, natural approach, communicative, and eclectic theories.

Ma (2021) presented findings on the effectiveness of immersive virtual contextual learning based on VR technologies from a constructivist perspective. Rinekso and Muslim (2020) considered the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the transformation of online learning modes. The authors emphasised the value of synchronous online discussions for teaching English in higher education despite acknowledging certain limitations in their implementation. In their 2020 study, Zhang and Zou identified five primary types of technology for learning foreign languages. Moreover, the authors demonstrated the latest technologies' four main goals and benefits: advancing practices, providing educational content, facilitating interaction, and restructuring learning approaches. Furthermore, these innovative technologies have been incorporated into various facets of language instruction and learning, with a positive outcome. Fitria (2020) observed that numerous linguistic tasks assist students in overcoming social isolation and provide opportunities for language development.

Irgasheva (2021) demonstrated the importance of enhancing students' professional speech competence using STEAM technologies in the context of English language teaching at technical higher education institutions. She presented an overview of the fundamental principles of modern approaches, suggestions, and recommendations for enhancing the informational and methodological support for developing communicative, linguistic, sociolinguistic, pragmatic, speech, and lexical competencies through STEAM technologies in teaching English to engineers. Sun et al. (2020) examined the potential applications of artificial intelligence in education. They employed a decision tree algorithm and neural network to construct a model for assessing English language teaching based on decision tree technologies.

In their study, Fenyi and Jones-Mensah (2022) presented a novel methodology for foreign language education in Ukraine, designated as HOTS, which has been demonstrated to be an efficacious pedagogical approach. In order to implement the HOTS concept in practice, educators must utilise specific teaching strategies, including posing open-ended questions, engaging students in group work and discussions, lecturing, encouraging students to create their materials, and providing constructive feedback. Singh (2020) analysed the findings to determine the extent of teachers' awareness of the practice of developing higher-order thinking skills (HOTS) in English language classes, their implementation, assessment, and the challenges they encounter. In a study published in 2022, Arini and Wahyudin presented findings on how students perceive the use of questioning techniques to enhance their higher-level language skills. It is of paramount importance that students develop their conversational skills and communication abilities, as their future professions may be largely dependent on these skills.

Prayudi et al. (2021) emphasised the need for educators to receive training on using technologies, particularly social networks. A review of previous research and publications revealed that utilising contemporary methodologies and trends can positively influence the advancement of communicative competence in higher education students. Nevertheless, it is essential to consider students' distinctive characteristics and the constraints associated with utilising cutting-edge educational technologies.

3 Methods

In order to gain a comprehensive understanding of the issue of implementing contemporary approaches and trends in the methodology of teaching foreign languages in higher education institutions, the following methods were employed: an analysis of scientific research and publications on the topic of the use of modern approaches and trends in foreign language teaching methodologies in higher education institutions. This method enables the identification of current trends and prospects in the use of technologies in foreign language learning and the identification of potential opportunities for improving the educational process in higher education institutions. The systematic analysis of contemporary trends has enabled the formation of a comprehensive view of the demands of educational service seekers and the possibilities of satisfying them. Theoretical modelling was employed while developing practical exercises to address current educational tasks.

4 Results

The contemporary teaching system is an eclectic mix of various techniques, methods, and approaches, emphasising the specific goals that need to be achieved for each student. These goals include deepening knowledge of grammar or vocabulary, improving conversational skills, advancing to the next level, or mastering a professional foreign language (Isaieva, 2024). One of the most innovative approaches to foreign language instruction involves virtual reality. The metaverse is an ambitious project that aims to create a virtual world that is simultaneously mapped and independent of the natural world in cyberspace. It will utilise the advancements of various digital technologies, including virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), big data, and 5G. It is crucial for the future development of various professions, including education. It represents the latest stage in the development of immersive technology. The essence of the metaverse is a digital online space that exists in parallel to the real world. This space provides a practical field for innovation and the development of human society. One notable advantage of the metaverse for foreign language learning is that it can provide an engaging and interactive educational field for both teachers and students, simultaneously satisfying needs in both the physical and virtual worlds (Foster & Shah, 2021).

The metaverse facilitates the creation of digital identities for teachers and students, provides access to formal and informal learning environments within the virtual realm, and enables participants in the educational process to interact in virtual locations. From the perspective of educational philosophy, the most notable advantage of the metaverse is its capacity to create an immersive interaction field for teachers and students (Sun et al., 2021).

The field of the metaverse in foreign language education transcends the limitations of the physical world, creating a new world of virtual education through an online educational space. It allows teachers and students to simultaneously meet natural and virtual learning needs in the physical and virtual worlds. However, the virtual world in the metaverse of foreign language education is neither a simple copy of the physical world nor a "parallel universe." The media-supporting characteristics of the metaverse can compensate for the shortcomings of the physical world and even surpass its limitations in some dimensions, forming a particular educational field of the metaverse that can have a general effect of presence (Guo & Gao, 2022).

The Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) approach facilitates the acquisition of knowledge in another discipline through a foreign language (Pasichnyk & Pasichnyk, 2023). Although these classes are conducted in a foreign language, the primary objective is to gain knowledge in another field. This method enables students to deepen their knowledge of a specific subject and practise communicative situations in a foreign language, significantly broadening their horizons and increasing the opportunities for language use.

Information and communication technologies are the only way to realise goals and strategies for implementing CLIL methodology and provide students with the most complete and profound cognitive, social, and personal development. They serve as the primary means of developing the concept of student-centred learning, implementing "flexible learning trajectories" and pedagogical methods, ensuring the quality of educational services, and forming an educational environment in higher education, which is defined as the conditions necessary for students to understand and comprehend the content of learning (Styrkina, 2020). In the task-based learning (TBL) methodology, the teacher initiates the lesson not by explaining a new topic but by assigning a task that the students must complete. Subsequently, the instructor assesses the student's work to ascertain the grammatical and lexical constructions employed. After the teacher elucidates the subject matter in question, facilitating the acquisition of new knowledge and enhancing comprehension (Sholeh et al., 2020). At the lesson's conclusion, the teacher proposes a new task, similar to the initial task, intending to consolidate the newly acquired material.

In order to achieve mastery of these skills, developers of educational online products have several options at their disposal. One of the most popular and user-friendly options is YouGlish. It is an online pronunciation dictionary based on YouTube. It offers users many authentic examples of how individuals pronounce a word or phrase in a specific context. A choice of three accents is available: The three accents available are British, American, and Australian. In addition to the videos, YouGlish includes a script with the word or phrase in question. For example, a search for "speaking skills" yielded 353 results, with 240 instances of the term pronounced in American English, 52 in British English, and 61 in Australian English. Applying the YouGlish platform facilitates the enhancement of pronunciation and the overall quality of the English language. The language base encompasses 16 languages.

Another valuable online resource is FORVO, an online platform that provides access to many audio files with accompanying pronunciation. The distinction between YouGlish and FORVO lies in the fact that users can create and upload their files, called clips, on FORVO. Moreover, they can vote for the most and least effective clips. The range of languages is more diverse than that of YouGlish. The most popular languages include German, Spanish, English, French, Portuguese, and Japanese. Furthermore, it is possible to search for pronunciations according to specific categories. In total, there are over 100 categories in English and other languages. The U.S. Department of State and its resource centre, American English, offer users a collection of situational dialogues titled "Dialogs for Everyday Use" for online speaking practice. Each dialogue is accompanied by Language Notes, where the authors briefly describe and explain the key phrases (Khatser, 2021).

To combine speaking and listening skills, teachers can integrate videos from ESL Video into the educational process. These videos are categorised according to the viewer's level: Beginner, Low Intermediate, Intermediate, High Intermediate, and Advanced. Each video has tasks, such as multiple-choice questions or fill-in-the-blanks, to be completed after viewing (Al-Khasawneh & Obeidallah, 2019). The resource authors provide a transcript of the material to assist with comprehension difficulties. For ease of searching, students can use the Categories tab. Additionally, ESL Conversation Cards can be used to simulate dialogues between people.

Interactive whiteboards and programs can help students learn languages faster and more effectively. For instance, the Rosetta Stone program utilises interactive exercises and images to enhance speaking and understanding. Interactive whiteboards also aid learning through interactive tasks and images. The Rosetta Stone program simulates real-life situations, allowing students to learn a foreign language through intuitive speech perception and repetition. It also includes interactive exercises and images that aid in developing pronunciation and grammatical skills.

Interactive whiteboards, such as the SMART Board, enable students to interact using their fingers or a particular marker. It allows the teacher to conduct lessons more interactively, creating games and exercises that let students interact with the learning material, making language learning more effective and engaging. Overall, interactive whiteboards and programs help students learn languages more interestingly, making the educational process more effective and exciting (Shamsitdinova, 2021).

5 Discussion

In the context of teaching a professional English course, where there is a great deal of complex vocabulary that can be considered passive, as well as a great many more straightforward vocabulary items that can be classified as active, it is of the utmost importance to develop an appropriate teaching methodology that would help students to effectively master and remember both types of words (Kintu et al., 2017).

One method for achieving this is through the utilisation of contextual vocabulary learning. It is recommended that students take notes on words encountered in different texts and situations to understand their meaning and the context of their usage. Furthermore, it is crucial to provide opportunities for the practical application of words, such as the construction of sentences or dialogues, to reinforce their retention in memory (Li & Flowerdew, 2020). It is beneficial for educators to provide supplementary information regarding the cultural and social implications of vocabulary usage, which can assist students in comprehending and recalling words more effectively. For instance, examples of passive words in films, music, literature, and other aspects of culture can be provided. It enhances the learning experience and fosters superior word retention, recalling them within a contextual framework rather than as isolated entities (Bilenka, 2021).

Consider several examples of exercises that can be employed to develop students' vocabulary:

1. Matching exercises: students need to match words with their definitions. They facilitate better assimilation of new vocabulary and understanding of word meanings. Using the platform YouGlish, students need to find videos in which the words from the exercise are used and listen to how they are used in a natural context. After this, students should determine the correspondence between the words and their definitions (Table 1).

Table 1. Example of task to correspond words with their definitions.

Concept	Definition
1. Leadership	A. The process of determining how to allocate financial resources.
2. Budgeting	B. The ability to motivate and guide a group of people towards a common goal.
3. Decision-making	C. The practice of analysing options and choosing the most effective course of action.
4. Strategic planning	D. Setting long-term goals and determining the best approach to achieve them.
5. Teamwork	E. Collaborative efforts of a group to accomplish a task or goal.

After completing the exercise, students can discuss their answers and resolve any issues that arose during the exercise.

2. Exercises on choosing the correct word: students must select

the correct word that fits the context. These exercises improve understanding of word usage in various situations and contexts.

Students need to choose the correct word that fits the context. Afterwards, they should use the FORVO platform to listen to the pronunciation of each word and ensure their choice is correct (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Example of exercise on choosing the correct word

1. The manager is responsible for _____ the team's progress and performance.
 - a) monitoring
 - b) evaluating
 - c) analysing
2. Effective _____ involves setting achievable goals and deadlines.
 - a) delegation
 - b) leadership
 - c) time management
3. Conflict _____ skills are crucial for resolving disputes in the workplace.
 - a) resolution
 - b) assessment
 - c) delegation

3. Sentence-building exercises: students must write sentences with the new words they learned. These exercises allow them to understand how to use the new vocabulary in real life and develop their written expression skills (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Example of sentence-building exercise

- strategic planning / involves / setting long-term goals / and / developing action plans;
- performance evaluation / helps / identify strengths / and / areas for improvement;
- effective communication / is essential / for building / strong relationships / with clients;
- risk assessment / involves / identifying potential threats / to / business operations;
- decision-making / requires / weighing options / and / considering potential outcomes.

4. Exercises on identifying synonyms and antonyms: students need to find synonyms and antonyms for words they have studied. These exercises help students expand their vocabulary and understand the nuances of word meanings. For example, find synonyms and antonyms for the given words: challenge, accomplishment, support, obstacle, encouragement.

Students can watch a video on the ESL Video platform that features real-life usage of these words. Afterwards, they can use these words in sentences to reinforce their usage and understanding.

5. Sentence completion exercises: students must complete sentences with missing words. These exercises help students develop skills in contextual understanding and word usage in sentences (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Example of sentence completion exercise

- Fill in the blanks in the sentences with words from the list (decision-making, leadership, conflict resolution, time management, performance evaluation):
- Effective _____ involves assessing options and choosing the best course of action.
 - _____ skills are crucial for guiding and motivating team members towards common goals.
 - _____ is important for identifying strengths and areas for improvement among employees.
 - Successful _____ requires prioritising tasks and maximising productivity.
 - Strong _____ skills are necessary for maintaining a positive work environment.

Upon completing the exercise, students may utilise the Rosetta Stone platform to verify the accuracy of their responses and further study vocabulary in context.

During this exercise, students learn to comprehend the nuances of word meanings and enrich their vocabulary (Lukas & Yunus, 2021).

The presented exercise options can be universally applied (Mohamad, 2018). Such exercises can be employed to develop both active and passive vocabulary, encompassing both general topics and professionally oriented terminology, irrespective of the language being studied. Furthermore, teachers have the option of selecting the optimal modern technologies that facilitate the process of studying a foreign language for professional purposes.

6 Conclusion

The requirements for the methodological support of foreign language teaching in higher education institutions necessitate constant dynamism and modernity to meet societal demands. Research findings indicate that the trends in teaching methodology are multifaceted and universal. The teacher acts as a connector between innovative developments, the content of the educational programme, and learners. Examples of the practical implementation of modern approaches and trends reflect potential opportunities in teaching professional foreign languages. Students can develop a vocabulary of professional terminology and higher-order thinking skills, which are essential in forming professional competence.

Given the chosen topic's prevalence in scholarly achievements, it is crucial to consider the dynamics and rapid changes of modern educational trends. Further research and development in this direction could contribute to renewing and optimising methodological approaches to foreign language teaching in Ukrainian higher education institutions.

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